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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Ophelia Speaks

She once loved.
She once trusted.
She once cared.
She once spoke.

But they told her
be uninvested,
be unswayed,
be unmoved,
be unvoiced.

So she learned to
devour her words before they left her lips,
swallow her questions before they reached their ears,
return the "sweet letters" unopened,
and practice silence until it felt like virtue.

One day, she dared to speak.
They looked away.
One day, she wept.
They corrected her.
She endured.
They praised her.

And still, the weight grew unbearable.
The wound seemed incurable.
The pain, intolerable.
And they called her mad, her mind unstable.

Yet she lives
answering emails through tears,
smiling through meetings,
cloaking bruises in fashion and style.

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She tells her story,
and the world asks her to prove it.
She sets boundaries,
and the world whispers, "you're too much."
She chooses herself,
and the world calls her selfish.

This is Ophelia's story.
She did not drown.
She is not crazy.
She rises, she lives.

She reaches out to every woman,
to rewrite the fate of "Ophelia,"
to claim her voice,
to be heard,
to live fully,
and to love herself without apology.